

“THE CORRELATION BETWEEN HIGHER EDUCATION LEADERS’ STRESS RESILIENCE AND MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVENESS”

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Abstract: Nowadays, the activities of higher education leaders are carried out under significant pressure and responsibility. This means that they may face considerable stress and pressure during their work. Competition among educational institutions, rapidly evolving innovative technologies, and working in a digital environment can have a psychological impact on any leader. Therefore, a leader must be stress-resilient so that stress does not negatively affect their management and decision-making processes.

Keywords: stress resilience, management quality, leadership effectiveness, higher education, managerial competence, decision-making

The 21st century is considered an era full of innovations and new developments. The world is continuously evolving day by day. Every day, numerous innovative ideas are being generated in all fields.

Nowadays, the functioning of higher education institutions is considered a highly important issue. This, in turn, requires that leaders managing these educational organizations possess well-developed skills, such as the ability to overcome difficult situations arising during their work, to avoid mistakes under pressure when making critical decisions, and to remain resilient to stress in a rapidly evolving innovative environment.

The ultimate goal of management is the optimization of a system's functioning, achieving the maximum possible beneficial effect with the least effort and cost.¹

It is known that management is carried out through the interaction of people, so the leader must take into account the laws that govern the dynamics of mental processes, interpersonal relationships, and group behaviors in their activities.²

The leader manages the entire activity of the organization. They are responsible for every issue, problem, success, and failure related to the organization. The leader is a leader precisely because they take on such great responsibility. Reviewing every task that needs to be resolved and making the final decision definitely falls on the leader’s shoulders.

In difficult situations, it is important for managerial personnel to complete their work successfully without falling into stress or experiencing excessive pressure. Nowadays, managerial personnel must have a very professional and thorough understanding of their work. They need to know how to conduct themselves in different situations and must possess all the skills and experience related to their profession. Having a good knowledge of their work guarantees that any person will not face unnecessary pressure or stress during the course of their job.

If a leader becomes occupied only with managerial tasks and personal matters, and remains indifferent to observing the people under their supervision, then such a leader should

¹ Т.С.Кабаченко, «Психология управления», Москва 2000

² D.I.Mukumova, R.X.Fayzullayev, A.A.Jumanov, S.B.Yarova, “Boshqaruv psixologiyasi”, Toshkent 2023

be replaced. Being unaware of the actions and behavior of members of the institution leads to the fragmentation of the team into several groups.³

Leader personnel activity is considered to consist of the management process. This includes managing the organization, making decisions, distributing tasks, setting goals, developing strategic plans and implementing them, enhancing the organization's reputation, and bringing it to a level where it possesses a distinct image, as well as many other responsibilities.

By being able to accept difficulties that arise during work without pressure or stress, a leader can serve as a positive example for their employees. This, in turn, strengthens employees' trust in the leader's competence and experience, which leads to the creation of a trust-based environment in the workplace.

In conclusion, the stress resilience of managerial staff undoubtedly has an impact on their management effectiveness. Leaders who do not lose control in stressful situations and are able to remain calm do not face significant difficulties in managing organizational activities. Such leaders create a healthy work environment within the team and can serve as a positive example for all employees. This is considered one of the key factors for an organization's success.

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3. Narzulla Boymurodov, "Rahbar psixologiyasi", Toshkent 2007

³ Narzulla Boymurodov, "Rahbar psixologiyasi", Toshkent 2007